

Length Frequencies and Length-Weight Relationship of Two Commercial Fish Species, *Tenualosa Ilisha* and *Otolithodies Pama* Catch by Trammel Net at Kalwe Village, Bilu Island

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Abstract

Biometric indices of length-weight relationships and length frequencies of two commercially important species; *Tenualosa ilisha* and *Otolithodies pama* were described from Mon Coastline. A total of 211 samples for *T. ilisha* species and 310 samples for *O. pama* species had been collected from fish landing sites, Kalwe village, Bilu Island during September, 2018 to May, 2019. The size ranges of 15- 43 cm for *T. ilisha* and 19-51cm for *O. pama* with different frequencies had been analyzed. In the value of regression coefficient ($b = 4.18$) for *T. ilisha* was significantly greater than 3.0 that is isometric growth while that of ($b = 2.12$) for *O. pama* was significantly smaller than the value of isometric growth. The growth pattern of *T. ilisha* was positive allometric and that of *O. pama* was negative and it had revealed the upset of different trophic levels and food chain of *O. pama* in the study area. The correlation coefficient of determination (R^2) were observed 0.71 for *T. ilisha* and that of 0.246 for *O. pama* during the study period.

Key words: coastline, species, landing sites, regression coefficient, isometric, allometric, food chain, trophic level, correlation coefficient, determination

Introduction

Myanmar riverine ecosystem had ended at Gulf of Mottama and carried organic debris those were rich of nutrients for aquatic fauna. Fishery resources are also rich and diverse in long coastal of Myanmar especially in Mon Coastal. Marine fishes occupied about 75 % of production, and 25 % from inland fishery in Myanmar. Fluctuation of sea water flooded and fresh water discharged and leading to dynamic estuaries of variation in physical factors (salinity and temperature) with 6-7 m of tide in this region. The scattered mangrove habitats also provide juveniles to feed and shelter until their gonads to be developed. Estuary ecosystem supports aquatic fauna and the livelihoods of 2,00000 people in this region where Ramsar site at 8 May covering 161,030 hectares (ramsar.org, 8.2.2020).

Bilu Island is 30 K long and coastal ecosystems degraded by economic growth and overexploitation. Declined in fish catch (50-90 %) over the past 10 years and fisher folk forced to migration (iucn.org, 15.10.19) and Kalwe village located at latitude 16°29'41" North longitude 97° 31'45" East. There are four fishery villages in Bilu Island but only drift net fishery is in Kalwe village. Commercial fishes are anchovy, bombay duck, hilsa, croaker and threadfin those had been purchased by the processing plants for export to Mawlamyine. The top fishes regarding with catch weight and values are Hilsa (Nga-Tha -louk), well known in Myanmar dishes and Croaker (Nga-Poke-Thin) which is the high price and its swim bladder is much in demand to China for soups and traditional medicines. The fishery closing season is from June to August in the fishing ground.

Length and weight relationship (LWR) is basic information to determine the weight of a fish if known length or length-frequency distribution (Koutrakis *et al.*, 2003). It is great

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importance in fishery biology, fishery management and their stock assessment (Haimoici and Velasco, 2000). The present work focused to fulfill the data gap for the length frequencies and LWR of two commercial species, *T. ilisha* (Hilsa) and *O. pama* (Croaker) from Kalwe fish landing, Mon Coastal. So, this work aims

- to estimate the length frequencies of two commercial fishes, *T. ilisha* and *O. pama*
- to assess the Length and weight relations of two commercial fishes, *T. ilisha* and *O. pama*
- to record the informative requirements regarding with certain base line data for fishery management

Materials and Method

Study site and study period: The fishery resources were collected from the fish landing site, Kalwe village (Bilu Island, Chaungson Township). The fishery is only intraditional practice drift net (trammel net) fishery and the study period lasted from September 2018 to May 2019.

Fishing ground and Fish landing site (Google map)

Sample collection: The specimens were randomly collected from three medium size boat in drift nets. The total of 310 specimens of *O. pama* and 211 of *T. ilisha* were sampled out randomly for analysis. The 20-50 specimens of each species had been collected monthly from subsample for measuring and recording length and weight as soon as landing hours.

Identification and classification: The classification system was adopted by Day (1878), Talwar, P.K and Jhingran, AG. (1991), fish base (fishbase.org, 12.5.2019) and Local name of the specimens followed after Tint Swe (2011).

Recording data for length-frequency and length-weight relationship: The minimum size range (15-19 cm) to the maximum range (>39-43 cm) for *T. ilisha*, and those of (19-23 cm) and

(>47-51 cm) for *O.pama* had been recorded with respective mass (g). The length- weight relationship was calculated by the method of least squares using the formula: $W = aL^b$ (Le Cren, 1951).

Interviewing: In conduction with fishery data surveyed, the present work used semi-structured interview and face to face was adopted. Interviews contained the questions on a day for fishing activity, time and duration of fishing trip to and from fishing ground and landing sites, catch size and composition, etc.

Data analysis: Analysis of all the recorded data was shown in graphic presentation. Monthly data record had been carried out and linear regression was used to analyze the length-weight relationship.

Results and discussion: Two commercial fish species of 310 specimens of *O.pama* (19-23 to > 47-51 cm), and 211 specimens of *T.ilisha* (15-19 to > 39-43 cm) had been recorded their length frequencies distribution with respective weight. Regarding with LWRs *Tenuialosa ilisha* ($R^2 = 0.7074$) with b (4.18) and in *Otolithoides pama*, ($R^2 = 0.2467$) with b (2.12) had been recorded. Rarely occurring of the larger size for both species indicated that overfishing in this fishing ground and others. Smaller fishes of *O. pama* (19-23 cm) are higher proportion of catch compared with the larger ones at September, November, January and April. The present finding was in accordance with (14 -19 cm) of dominant catch in Kyeikohto fishing ground (Thazin Htet, 2017) but the maximum size of this fish was (160 cm) (www.fishbase.se , 6/ 2017). These fishes could not allow to be recurring of Juveniles to aquatic ecosystem and affecting sustainable fishery.

Driftnet (Trammel net)

Medium-sized boat

Table 1. Measurements of gear and vessel

Boat Size	Dimension Boat (L x W x D)cm	Net Mesh Size (cm)	Net Height (cm)	Preservation
Medium	(1050 x 120 x 195) (one piston)	7.4	480	Cold Chain in Ice

T.ilisha

O.pama

length weight relationship of *T. ilisha*

The size of *T. ilisha* (35.37 cm) was dominant in monsoon and 36.84 cm in winter from Hooghly-Matlah estuarine, West Bengal, India (Dibakar Bhakta, 2018) but the present finding compared with above author indicating some smaller size range of 15-43cm. Regression coefficient 'b' is larger or smaller than 3.0 indicating allometric growth (Ricker, 1973). Negative allometric growth b (2.12) presenting the fish become slender increment in weight and lower correlation ($R^2 = 0.246$) in *O. pama*. The findings of the present work did not coincide with b values (2.88, 2.84 and 2.86) with R^2 (0.96, 0.95 and 0.95) for male, female and pooled samples from the Hooghly-Matlah estuarine, West Bengal, India (Dibakar *et al.*, 2019). Positive allometric growth, b (4.18) shown relatively stouter bodied and correlation ($R^2 = 0.71$) in *T. ilisha* (Riedel *et al.*, 2007). LWR of male and female *T. ilisha* – b (3.04 and 3.07) while R^2 (0.90 and 0.822) from Meghna River, Chandpur District, Bangladesh (Flura *et al.*, 2015). Decreasing trend of fish stock had been recorded especially in Croaker at Thanlwin River Mouth (Thet Htwe Aung, 2018). Pollution, overexploitation, ineffective management and lack of information on growth in some cases may be affecting the decreasing marine fishery (Tasuba, 2016). Declined in catch of drift net fishery in Bilu Island, Mon coastal water coincided with above authors.

Conclusion

Transporting boats landed within three days in the former years but later now. Less catch of fishing may be time consuming and higher cost. Smaller size of fish in catch reduced total biomass and not marketable. But the fishery contributes job opportunities of fishermen and young female workers for post harvesting industry. Fishery had been facing a decline dramatically in one third compared with that of 2017 (Interview survey). Small mesh size and sand mine in estuaries, climate change and plastic pollution may be threatened factors for the fishing ground.

As a conclusion biometric indices of LWRs shown that *T. ilisha* was growing well but *O. pama* facing with the upset of growth pattern. Limiting mesh size should be to escape the smaller size of *O. pama*. Addressing the further research should be done these fish stock spawn where and when taking place. Better resource management plan will be needed to be sustainable fishery and Coastal resources in Mon State, Gulf of Mottama.

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